

**COMPUTER MODELLING OF CALCULATING FUNCTIONS OF ONE
VARIABLE AND THEIR DERIVATIVES.**

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Annotation: Presented the scheme of piecewise polynomial calculation of functions of one real variable based on Newton's interpolation polynomial. The segment is divided into subintervals, at each of which the function is approximated by the arithmetic mean of Newton's polynomials for forward and backward interpolation. Developed Software for calculating functions of one variable and derivatives, where the number of subintervals and the degree of the polynomial are selected programmatically in such a way as to minimize the absolute error in the approximation of the function and their derivatives. Comparative results of numerical experiments are presented.

Key words: Piecewise polynomial scheme; function approximation; absolute error of functions, approximation of derivatives of functions.

Introduction

There is a wide range of computer problems in which the calculation of functions is used. At the same time, in practical applications, as a rule, the methods for calculating functions are required: high speed, high accuracy of their approximation, computational stability, minimum consumption of RAM and computational resources, versatility of the calculation scheme [1].

For example, complex multidimensional modeling problems in low-dimensional systems, which must be solved within a strictly limited time, in the solution algorithms contain a large set of various schemes for computing functions [2]. Computer implementation of such circuits in general and the computation of functions in them in particular requires high performance and high computation accuracy [3]. One of the typical examples is the study of exciton states in systems of reduced dimension (quantum wells, quantum wires, quantum dots and superlattices), which occupies one of the central places in condensed matter physics [4,5].

Computational schemes for approximating functions were considered in many papers, for example, in [6] developed and investigated parallel schemes for digital signal processing based on minimizing the time complexity of computing functions, in [7] developed parallelizable piecewise polynomial schemes for approximating functions, derivatives and calculating definite integrals with increased accuracy using Gaussian polynomials, in [8] considered schemes for the approximate calculation of definite integrals using a piecewise polynomial scheme, in [9] investigated conflict-free and stable methods of deterministic parallel processing based on segments of a series in Chebyshev polynomials, in [10] considered the using a subspace iteration with Chebyshev polynomial filtering to calculate a self-consistent-field, in [11] numerically investigated the dependences of the effective potential and binding energy of an exciton on the magnetic field for various values.

In this paper, described a computer model for calculating functions of one variable. A distinctive feature of the scheme presented in the article is the use of the

half-sum of interpolation polynomials as an approximant [12], where Newton's polynomials are used to interpolate forward and backward from which the arithmetic mean value is taken at each subinterval. On the basis of this technique, a significant increase in the accuracy of the computer piecewise polynomial approximation of the function and derivatives is achieved, and, in this method, the accuracy is increased without increasing the time complexity.

1. Scheme for approximating functions of one variable using Newton's polynomials for forward and backward interpolation.

Below is a scheme for approximating the function

$$y = f(x), \tag{1}$$

where $x \in [a, b] \subset R, (x, y) \in R^2, a, b < \infty$.

Within the framework of the described approach [6,7], the segment [a, b] is covered by a system of equal disjoint subintervals of the form

$$[a, b] = \bigcup_{i=0}^{P-2} [x_i, x_{i+1}) \cup [x_{P-1}, x_P], \tag{2}$$

where $P = 2^k, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, x_0 = a, x_P = b$.

Interpolating Newton polynomials are constructed at the nodes located in closed intervals $[x_i, x_{i+1}]$. In the subsequent calculation of the approximating polynomial for unambiguous addressing within the boundaries x_i, x_{i+1} of subintervals (2) by the number i to the array of coefficients of the approximating polynomial, all subintervals are considered open to the right as intervals of the form $[x_i, x_{i+1})$ from (2).

Next, restrictions are introduced on the number of subintervals and the degree of the interpolating polynomial of the form:

$$k \leq k_0, \quad n \leq n_0, \tag{3}$$

where $n_0 = const$ is the a priori specified value of the upper bound for the degree of the approximating polynomial, $k_0 = const$ is the a priori specified upper bound for k from (2).

On each subinterval (2), taking into account conditions (3), an approximating polynomial of degree n of the form

$$P_{ni}(x) = \frac{P_{ni}^{old}(x) + P_{ni}^{ort}(x)}{2}, \tag{4}$$

where $P_{ni}^{old}(x)$, $P_{ni}^{ort}(x)$ - is Newton's polynomial for forward and backward interpolation, respectively, i - is the number of the subinterval (2). The degree n of polynomial (4) is chosen to be the same for all subintervals (2) and minimum if the condition

$$|f(x) - P_{ni}(x)| \leq \varepsilon, \tag{5}$$

where ε - is the a priori given boundary of the approximation error of function (1), $i = \overline{0, P-1}$ is the number of the subinterval (2).

Condition (5) is checked on all subintervals at points that do not coincide with the interpolation nodes and follow with a priori given uniform test step, the length of which is a parameter of the algorithm and is chosen knowingly smaller than the interpolation step.

Algorithm 1 is used to determine the degree n of polynomial (4) and the parameter k from (2).

Algorithm 1. Block-scheme of piecewise polynomial approximation of functions of one variable

where ε is the boundary of the absolute approximation error, k_0 is the a priori specified upper boundary for k from (2), n_0 is the a priori specified value of the upper boundary of the degree of the approximating polynomial.

According to Algorithm 1, the calculation of the coefficients of the polynomial (4) begins with the exponent $n = 1$ at $k = 0$. If it is impossible to reach the specified limit of the absolute error ε from (5), the value of n is increased by 1; this continues until n goes out of range (3); if they are violated, a transition is made again to the minimum value $n = 1$, but already for $k = 1$, and so on.

Polynomial (4) is transformed with respect to distributivity, bringing similar ones to the form

$$P_{ni}(x) = \sum_{j=0}^n B_{fij} x^j, \quad (6)$$

where f - is the index corresponding to the function being approximated, i - is the number of the subinterval from (2), $x \in [x_i, x_{i+1})$, $i = \overline{0, P-1}$, $n = \text{const}$.

If a combination of numbers n, k , for which the constructed polynomial (6) satisfies inequality (5) on all subintervals (2) is found, then for function (1) and for each subinterval (2) the coefficients of polynomial (6), total values $2^k(n+1)$, can be saved to computer memory. Further, to calculate the value of function (1), it is enough to decrypt the subinterval number

$$i = \left[\frac{x - \alpha}{h_p} \right] \quad (7)$$

with time complexity

$$t = O(1)$$

where $[\alpha]$ - is the integer part of the α , and h_p - is the length of the subinterval (2), $h_p = x_i - x_{i+1}$, $i = \overline{0, P-1}$. The resulting value i - is the index of the row in the two-dimensional array B_{fij} of the coefficients $B_{fij}(j = \overline{0, n}, i = \overline{0, P-1})$, which stores the sample of values B_{fij} for the function (1) (the dimension corresponding to the number of the function f is not taken into account).

Since the coefficients of polynomial (6) are stored in the computer memory, the time of its calculation according to the Horner scheme is estimated from the expression

$$t(1) = n(t_k + t_q), \quad n = const, \quad (8)$$

where t_k, t_q - is the time of binary multiplication and addition, respectively.

The degree of polynomial (6) chosen according to Algorithm 1 is minimal on 2^k subintervals, thereby minimizing the time complexity of calculating the function for the a priori specified error boundary (5). Subject to the reservations made based on (8)

$$t(1) = O(1)$$

In the form (6), the approximating polynomial is used below for numerical differentiation and approximate calculation of derivatives, while the derivative of function (1) is approximated by the derivative of the polynomial, and the antiderivative of the function is the antiderivative of the polynomial.

By construction, the scheme is invariant with respect to the number i of the subinterval (2), the number P of subintervals, and also with respect to the degree of the polynomial (4). Therefore, further mathematical constructions are carried out for the current number of the subinterval (2), $i = \overline{0, P-1}$, and for the current values of n, k .

Subinterval (2) is covered by a grid of equally spaced nodes of the form

$$x_{i,l} = x_i + lh, \quad (9)$$

where $l = \overline{0, n}$, h - is the interpolation step -

$$h = \frac{x_{i+1} - x_i}{n}. \quad (10)$$

At the nodes (9), a Newton polynomial is constructed for forward interpolation [13]:

$$P_{ni}^{old}(x) = f(x_{i,0}) + \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\Delta^j y_{i,0}}{j! h^j} \prod_{l=0}^{j-1} (x - x_{i,l}), \quad (11)$$

where $x \in [x_i, x_{i+1}]$.

Similarly, on the segment $x \in [x_i, x_{i+1}]$ at the nodes (9), a Newton polynomial is constructed for backward interpolation [13]:

$$P_{ni}^{ort}(x) = f(x_{i,n}) + \sum_{J=1}^n \frac{\Delta^J y_{i,n-J}}{j! h^J} \prod_{m=0}^{J-1} (x - x_{i,n-m}) \quad (12)$$

For the purpose of further transformations, the finite differences of the first order $\Delta y_{i,0} = f(x_{i,1}) - f(x_{i,0})$ and the finite differences of the kth order $\Delta^k y_{i,0} = \Delta^{k-1} y_{i,1} - \Delta^{k-1} y_{i,0}$ are calculated, followed by $i = \overline{0, P-1}$ in the notations

$$b_{ij}^{old} = \frac{\Delta^j y_{i,0}}{j!}, \quad (13)$$

$$b_{ij}^{ort} = \frac{\Delta^j y_{i,n-j}}{j!}, \quad (14)$$

polynomials (11), (12) take the form, respectively

$$P_{ni}^{old}(x) = f(x_{i,0}) + \sum_{J=1}^n \frac{b_{ij}^{old}}{h^J} \prod_{l=0}^{J-1} (x - x_{i,l}), \quad (15)$$

$$P_{ni}^{ort}(x) = f(x_{i,n}) + \sum_{J=1}^n \frac{b_{ij}^{ort}}{h^J} \prod_{m=0}^{J-1} (x - x_{i,n-m}). \quad (16)$$

where $x \in [x_i, x_{i+1}]$.

In equation (15), introduce the variable

$$t = \frac{x - x_{i,0}}{h}, \quad (17)$$

where h is from (10), brings polynomial (15) to the form

$$P_{ni}^{old}(t(x)) = f(x_{i,0}) + \sum_{J=1}^n b_{ij}^{old} \prod_{l=0}^{J-1} (t - l), \quad (18)$$

where $t \in [0, n]$.

In equation (16), introduce the variable

$$q = \frac{x - x_{i,m}}{h} \quad (19)$$

where h is from (10), brings polynomial (16) to the form

$$P_{ni}^{ort}(q(x)) = f(x_{i,n}) + \sum_{J=1}^n b_{ij}^{ort} \prod_{m=0}^{J-1} (q + m), \quad (20)$$

where $q \in [-n, 0]$.

In order to bring polynomial (4) to the form (6), used a matrix scheme for calculating the coefficients of the polynomials by its roots [14]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} d_{j,j}^{(*)} \\ d_{j,(j-1)}^{(*)} \\ d_{j,(j-2)}^{(*)} \\ \vdots \\ d_{j,1}^{(*)} \\ d_{j,0}^{(*)} \end{pmatrix} = \prod_{l=1}^j \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ -z_{j-l} & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -z_{j-l} & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & -z_{j-l} & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -z_{j-l} \end{pmatrix} \quad (21)$$

where $d_{j,l}^{(*)}$ are the coefficients of the $R_{n,j}^{fwd}(t), R_{n,j}^{bkw}(q)$ polynomials, respectively, $z_l = l$ are the roots of the polynomials $R_{n,j}^{fwd}(t), R_{n,j}^{bkw}(q), l = \overline{0, j-1}, j = \overline{0, n}$

$$R_{n,j}^{fwd}(t) = \prod_{l=0}^{j-1} (t-l) = \sum_{l=0}^j d_l^{fwd} t^l, \quad (22)$$

$$R_{n,j}^{bkw}(q) = \prod_{m=0}^{j-1} (q+m) = \sum_{m=0}^j d_m^{bkw} q^m. \quad (23)$$

Taking into account equations (22), (23), polynomials (18), (20) take the form, respectively

$$P_{ni}^{old}(t(x)) = f(x_{i,0}) + \sum_{J=1}^n b_{ij}^{old} \sum_{l=0}^J d_l^{old} t^l, \quad (24)$$

$$P_{ni}^{ort}(q(x)) = f(x_{i,n}) + \sum_{J=1}^n b_{ij}^{ort} \sum_{m=0}^J d_m^{ort} q^m. \quad (25)$$

Expanding the brackets and reducing similar ones in polynomials (24), (25) will entail the equations

$$P_{ni}^{old}(t(x)) = \sum_{J=0}^n \alpha_{ij}^{old} t^J, \quad (26)$$

$$P_{ni}^{ort}(q(x)) = \sum_{J=0}^n \alpha_{ij}^{ort} q^J, \quad (27)$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_{i,0}^{old} = f(x_{i,0}), \\ \alpha_{i,j}^{old} = \sum_{m=j}^n b_{i,m}^{old} d_{j,m}^{old}, \\ j = \overline{1, n}, \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_{i,0}^{ort} = f(x_{i,n}), \\ \alpha_{i,j}^{ort} = \sum_{m=j}^n b_{i,m}^{ort} d_{j,m}^{ort}, \\ j = \overline{1, n}. \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

Let us pass in polynomial (27) to the variable t from (17), taking into account that

$$t - q = n. \quad (30)$$

Expressing q from (30) and substituting into (27), we obtain

$$P_{ni}^{ort}(t(x)) = \sum_{j=0}^n \alpha_{ij}^{ort} (t-n)^j \quad (31)$$

Applying the Newton binomial to the brackets $(t-n)^j$ in (31) implies:

$$P_{ni}^{ort}(t(x)) = \sum_{l=0}^n \alpha_{i,l}^{ort} \sum_{j=0}^l (-1)^{l-j} C_j^l n^{l-j} t^j = \sum_{j=0}^n \sum_{l=j}^n \alpha_{i,l}^{ort} (-1)^{l-j} C_j^l n^{l-j} t^j,$$

whence follows

$$P_{ni}^{ort}(t(x)) = \sum_{j=0}^n A_{i,j}^{ort} t^j, \quad (32)$$

where

$$A_{i,j}^{ort} = \sum_{l=j}^n \alpha_{i,l}^{ort} (-1)^{l-j} C_j^l n^{l-j}. \quad (33)$$

Taking into account (28), (33) the sought-for approximating polynomial (4) on the subinterval $[x_i, x_{i+1}]$ from (2), $i = \overline{0, P-1}$, takes the form

$$P_{ni}(t(x)) = \sum_{j=0}^n B_{i,j} t^j, \quad (34)$$

where t from (17),

$$B_{i,j} = \frac{A_{i,j}^{ort} + \alpha_{i,j}^{old}}{2}. \quad (35)$$

As noted above, after the coefficients (35) are calculated, according to Algorithm 1, condition (5) is checked, if polynomial (34) satisfies inequality (5) at all check points, then the constructed polynomial (34) with coefficients (35) is taken as the required polynomial of the form (4).

The approximating polynomial in the form (34) is calculated according to Horner's scheme

$$P_{ni}(t) = \left(\dots \left(B_{i,n}t + B_{i,(n-1)} \right) t + B_{i,(n-2)} \right) t + \dots + B_{i,0}, \quad (36)$$

where t from (17).

By virtue of its construction on the basis of interpolation, the algorithm using (34) - (36) is applicable for approximating a wide class of functions, while, as will be illustrated by a numerical experiment, it achieves a high approximation accuracy with low time complexity.

Scheme for approximation of derivatives of functions.

Below we present a scheme for approximating the derivatives of function (1) based on the scheme for approximating functions (34), (35).

Let the polynomial (34) with coefficients (35) be constructed, then the approximate equality holds on the i^{th} subinterval(2):

$$f(x) \approx P_{ni}(t(x)). \quad (37)$$

Assuming the existence of the derivative $(f(x))'_x$, we differentiate the left and right sides of expression (37) with respect to the variable x, we obtain

$$(f(x))'_x \approx P_{ni}(t(x))'_t t'_x, \quad (38)$$

whence, taking into account the equality following from (17): $t'_x = 1/h$ h - from (10), it follows

$$\left(P_{ni}(t(x)) \right)'_x = \frac{1}{h} \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} B_{i,j+1} t^j. \quad (39)$$

After decoding (7) i of the subinterval (2), the value of the polynomial on the right-hand side of equality (39) can be calculated according to Horner's scheme of the form

$$P'_{ni}(t) = \left(\left(\dots \left(nB_{n,i}t + (n-1)B_{n-1,i} \right) t + \dots + 2B_{n-2,i} \right) t + B_{1,i} \right) \frac{1}{h}. \quad (40)$$

2. Numerical experiment of the absolute error of approximation of the function and their derivatives

For the numerical experiment, used the module “Pogreshnost” of the software “Program for calculating functions of one variable, derivatives and integrals”.

The absolute error of approximation of a function is understood as

$$\delta_f = |f(x) - P_{ni}(x)| \quad (41)$$

Figure: 1. Software module "Pogreshnost" finding the absolute error of approximation of the function

The absolute error of approximation of the derivative is understood as

$$\delta_{f'} = |f'(x) - P'_{ni}(x)| \quad (42)$$

Figure: 2. Software module "Pogreshnost" finding the absolute error of approximation of the derivative of a function

where k is from (2), values (41), (42) are calculated at check points located uniformly over the entire segment $[a, b]$ from (2) with a priori given step.

A numerical experiment was carried out using the program complex "Program for calculating functions of one variable, derivatives and integrals" in the program module "Pogreshnost" which was developed in the IDE Delphi 10.2, for floating point numbers used the type extended with 18-19 significant digits, all experiments were carried out for $[a, b] = [0, 1]$.

3. Discussion and comparison of results

The schemes described below are compared with similar schemes based on Gauss polynomials [7] and on the basis of series segments in Chebyshev polynomials [9]; the schemes are also compared with the MathCad computer mathematics package. Below is a comparison of the absolute error of approximation of functions and their derivatives.

Table 1 presents errors of the form (41) of the $y = \frac{1}{1+e^{2x}}$ function using various approximation schemes

Table 1.

x	The proposed scheme	Gaussian polynomial	Chebyshev polynomial	MathCad package
0.00E+000 0	1.877E- 20	0.000E+0 0	5.164E- 15	5.551E- 17
1.00E- 0001	2.710E- 20	4.307E- 14	4.904E- 15	5.551E- 17
2.00E- 0001	2.710E- 20	2.070E- 14	1.520E- 15	5.551E- 17
3.00E- 0001	2.710E- 20	1.939E- 14	1.531E- 15	2.775E- 17

4.00E-0001	2.710E-20	3.548E-14	5.015E-15	2.775E-17
5.00E-0001	5.421E-20	0.000E+00	5.384E-15	5.551E-17
6.00E-0001	0.000E+00	1.668E-13	4.853E-15	2.775E-17
7.00E-0001	1.084E-19	4.186E-14	1.436E-15	2.775E-17
8.00E-0001	1.084E-19	2.701E-14	1.387E-15	5.551E-17
9.00E-0001	0.000E+00	3.806E-14	4.378E-15	5.551E-17

From table 1 that the boundary of the absolute error of approximation of the function $y = \frac{1}{1+e^{2x}}$ according to the proposed scheme (34), (35) is 6-7 orders of magnitude less than the error of the scheme based on Gaussian polynomials [7], 5 decimal orders less than the error of approximation by series in polynomials Chebyshev [9], and also two orders of magnitude less than when using the MathCad package.

Table 2 shows the error (42) of the approximation of the derivative of the function $y = x \operatorname{arctg}(x)$.

Table 2.

x	The proposed scheme	Gaussian polynomial	Chebyshev polynomial	MathCad package
0.00E+0000	3.401E-17	4.768E-7	9.536E-07	1.387E-15

1.00E-0001	7.616E-18	6.544E-7	1.869E-07	7.494E-16
2.00E-0001	2.141E-18	8.817E-8	5.290E-07	1.387E-15
3.00E-0001	8.131E-19	8.829E-7	4.816E-07	1.110E-15
4.00E-0001	1.409E-18	2.126E-7	1.417E-07	2.109E-15
5.00E-0001	7.464E-17	3.051E-7	6.103E-07	1.443E-15
6.00E-0001	7.426E-18	3.609E-7	1.031E-07	1.554E-15
7.00E-0001	4.119E-18	4.295E-8	2.577E-07	6.217E-15
8.00E-0001	1.301E-18	3.900E-7	2.127E-07	1.776E-15
9.00E-0001	1.398E-17	8.733E-8	5.821E-08	2.153E-14

From table 2 that the absolute error of numerical differentiation according to the modified scheme (34), (35) is 10-11 orders of magnitude less than the absolute error of the scheme based on Gaussian polynomials [7], 9-11 orders of magnitude less than the error of approximation by series in polynomials Chebyshev [9], 3-4 orders of magnitude less than when using the MathCad package.

Scheme (38), (35) is aimed at creating a software package that approximates the derivatives of frequently occurring functions, for example, in computer modeling of objects and devices of nanoelectronics [15], while, due to mathematical modification, it can significantly reduce the boundary of the absolute approximation error and the actual time complexity programs.

Conclusion

The proposed scheme for calculating real functions of one variable, which differs from analogs in the method of construction based on averaging Newton's interpolation polynomials for forward and backward interpolation on each subinterval, which allows an order of magnitude to reduce the boundaries of the absolute approximation errors.

Has been developed software for the implementation of the proposed varieties of piecewise polynomial schemes, ensures minimization of their time complexity, on its basis a numerical experiment has been carried out and results have been obtained that confirm a significant reduction in the absolute error in calculating functions and their derivatives, in comparison with schemes based on Gaussian polynomials [7], series in Chebyshev polynomials [9], including with methods of the MathCad package.

The presented approach, in addition to the purpose stated in the future, is expedient for creating a library of algorithms for calculating frequently used functions, which makes it possible to significantly reduce the time of numerical experiments when carrying out computer modeling, as well as to increase the accuracy of the physical characteristics and calculation of exciton states.

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